

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE COMPLICATION OF INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG ADOLESCENTS AT SELECTED COMMUNITY AREA PUDUCHERRY

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Internet addiction can gradually isolate you. You may develop an aversion to meeting and communicating with people in real life. This can impair your social skills and make you socially awkward.

Methodology: The research approach used for this study was quantitative research approach. A descriptive research design was adopted for this present study. By using convenient sampling technique, 30 adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

Results: Out of 30 samples, 27(90%) of them have Low level complication of internet addiction, 3(10%) of them have high level complication of internet addiction. The findings reveal that mean (93.43) and standard deviation (5.93) of the risk factors of internet addiction among adolescents. **Conclusion:** The study findings concluded that that samples were having average knowledge regarding consequences of internet addiction. Mean value of level of knowledge is 21.45. The demographic variables were found to be having non-significant association with knowledge regarding consequences of internet addiction.

Keywords: Internet addiction, Adolescents, Complications

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INTRODUCTION:

Internet addiction (IA) is a growing concern among adolescents, with many engaging in the internet for academic and recreational purposes. The bio psychosocial model of disease suggests that genetic factors, psychological components, and social factors contribute to IA. The author believes that the bio psychosocial model of disease is a feasible explanation for IA, as it considers biological vulnerability, cognitive errors, negative effects, personality traits, and the inert qualities of the internet itself.

Symptoms of IA include excessive internet usage, depression, mood swings, irritability, unsuccessful attempts to reduce internet usage, constant problems in personal relationships, education, and jobs due to incessant internet usage, lying to close ones, and using the internet to escape real-world problems. Males are significantly more addicted than females.

In India, where one of the fastest-growing information technology industries prevails, qualitative research has reported that adolescence is a risk factor for IA. Adolescents with deficient real-life social skills may find it easier to have online relationships, as there is no pressure of real-life eye-to-eye contacts, gestures, and human touch. They may overuse virtual realities offered by attractions in the internet to fill the voids of boredom and loneliness of real life.

Living in metropolitan areas is associated with problem use of the Internet, but it is unclear whether this is due to wider availability of the Internet or poor adult supervision. Students not living with a biological parent, low parental involvement, and parental unemployment have shown the highest relative risks of both problem use and addiction of the Internet.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to assess the complication of internet addiction among adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the level of knowledge on complication of internet addiction among adolescents at selected community area
- To find the association between the level of knowledge with their selected demographic variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

RESEARCH APPROACH:

A quantitative research approach was adopted for this present study.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

A descriptive research design was adopted for this present study.

SETTING OF THE STUDY:

The study was conducted among adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

POPULATION:

The target population for this study includes all the among adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

SAMPLE:

In the study, the sample comprises of among adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

SAMPLE SIZE:

In this study, the sample size consists of 30 adolescents at selected community area Puducherry.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

A purposive sampling technique was adopted for this study

CRITERIA FOR SAMPLE SELECTION:**INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- Adolescents includes both male and female
- Adolescents who are willing to participate in data collection
- Adolescents available at the time of data collection.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Adolescents that is not willing to participate in the study.

MAJOR FINDING

The study result shows that out of the People who were interviewed, Majority of the children 13(44%) were in the age group above 12-14 years. Most of the children 26(87%) were male. Most of the children father are graduate 13 (43%). Most of their father working as government employee 12(40%). Majority of their mothers 18(60%) also working as private employees joy type is unemployed. Most of them 30(100%) belongs rural area. Majority of them 17(57%) had awareness of hazards of the electronic devices. Among 30 only 19 (63%) had no mobile phones. But 13(43%) of them using mobile phones and 19(64%) they using minimum two hours a day Out of 30 samples, 27(90%) of them have Low level complication of internet addiction, 3(10%) of them have high level complication of internet addiction. The findings reveal that mean (93.43) and standard deviation (5.93) of the risk factors of internet addiction among adolescents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study result shows that out of the People who were interviewed, Majority of the children 13(44%) were in the age group above 12-14 years. Most of the children 26(87%) were male. Most of the children father are graduate 13 (43%). Most of their father working as government employee 12(40%). Majority of their mothers 18(60%) also working as private employees joy type is unemployed. Most of them 30(100%) belongs rural area. Majority of them 17(57%) had awareness of hazards of the electronic devices. Among 30 only 19 (63%) had no mobile phones. But 13(43%) of them using mobile phones and 19(64%) they using minimum two hours a day Out of 30 samples, 27(90%) of them have Low level complication of internet addiction, 3(10%) of them have high level complication of internet addiction The findings reveal that mean (93.43) and standard deviation (5.93) of the risk factors of internet addiction among adolescents

Table 1: Frequency and percentage wise distribution of the complication of internet addiction among adolescents [N= 30]

SCORING INTERPRETATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Low level complication of internet addiction	27	90
High level complication of internet addiction	3	10

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of the complication of internet addiction among adolescents

[N = 30]

MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
39.43	5.93

The above tables Shows that area wise Mean and Standard deviation of the complication of internet addiction among adolescents. The findings reveal that mean (93.43) and standard deviation (5.93) of the risk factors of internet addiction among adolescents. Association on assess the knowledge of the complication of internet addiction among adolescents at selected community area with their selected demographic variables. The chi square reveals that it is statistically association with age of the children to $p < 0.001$ significance other ore non significance

RECOMMENDATIONS

- A large-scale study can be done for replication to standardize.
- A comprehensive study can be conducted on knowledge in various settings.
- An experimental study can be conducted to make this more serious in the community.

CONCLUSION

The present study is descriptive study to assess the level of knowledge regarding consequences of internet addiction. The study findings revealed that samples were having average knowledge regarding consequences of internet addiction. Mean value of level of knowledge is 21.45. The demographic variables were found to be having non-significant association with knowledge regarding consequences of internet addiction.

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